

On the p_H of Sols after Coagulation with Electrolytes.

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The present paper records the following measurements :

(1) The p_H of a ferric hydroxide sol (A) on the addition of increasing quantities of solid KCl, KBr, K_2SO_4 and KNO_3 .

(2) The p_H of an arsenious sulphide sol on the addition of increasing quantities of solid KCl and KBr.

(3) The p_H and Cl^- ion concentrations for (a) an aluminium hydroxide sol with the addition of increasing concentrations of K_2SO_4 , $K_2C_2O_4$, KNO_3 , $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, $NaNO_3$, $Na_2C_2O_4$, and KCl solutions, and (b) a ferric hydroxide sol in contact with K_2SO_4 , $K_2C_2O_4$, KNO_3 , $NaNO_3$ and $Na_2C_2O_4$ solutions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Sols.

Ferric hydroxide sol.—10 C c. of a saturated solution of ferric chloride were added drop by drop to 500 c.c. of boiling conductivity water and the resulting sol was dialysed with frequent changes of distilled water until the dialysate was practically free from chloride. The sol was then stocked in wide mouthed Jena glass bottles.

Two such samples (A and B) were used in the course of the work in the present paper.

Arsenious sulphide sol.—A saturated solution of arsenious oxide was mixed with twice its volume of conductivity water. One litre of the diluted solution was added to a litre of conductivity water saturated with hydrogen sulphide, a gentle stream of which was continued till only a trace of arsenious acid was left free in the solution.

Aluminium hydroxide sol.—The aluminium hydroxide solution was prepared by adding slightly less than the equivalent amount of ammonium hydroxide solution (N/10) slowly and with vigorous stirring to a solution of aluminium chloride (N/10). The resulting sol was purified by dialysis in a parchment bag against repeated changes of distilled water, until a turbid sol was obtained.

Measurement of p_H values.—The p_H values were measured by the colorimetric method or by means of quinhydrone electrode or H_2

electrode against *N*-calomel electrode. A Hahn type (Hartmann and Braun, No. 16013) potentiometer was employed for measurement of *e.m.f.*

Measurement of Cl' ion concentrations.—The Cl' ion concentrations with both Al(OH)₃ and Fe(OH)₃ sols were measured by means of the Ag-AgCl electrode (*cf.* Noyes and Ellis, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 2532).

Procedure.

In order to avoid the dilution of the sol on the addition of an electrolyte solution to a definite volume of the sol (ferric hydroxide sol A and the arsenious sulphide sol) weighed amounts of different solid electrolytes were added, the mixture was centrifuged and the *p_H* of the supernatant liquid determined either by the colorimetric or by the *e.m.f.* method.

In the case of ferric hydroxide sol (B) and aluminium hydroxide sol, 25 c.c. of the pure sol were in each case mixed with 25 c.c. of electrolyte and water and the mixtures were allowed to remain in contact for 16 hours. Where coagulation took place, the mixture was centrifuged and the *p_H* and Cl' ion concentrations of the supernatant liquid were measured. Duplicate observations were taken in several cases. The results are reproducible. Concentration term in Tables I, II and III denotes concentration in g. equivalent per litre. 25 C c. of sol were taken in the case of the data in Tables I—III. All measurements were taken at room temperature.

TABLE I.

		<i>Ferric hydroxide sol (A).</i>			
KCl	{ Conc.	0.215	0.325	0.430	0.537
	{ <i>p_H</i>	4.88*	5.06*	5.35*	5.59*
KBr	{ Conc.	0.134	0.201	0.268	0.335
	{ <i>p_H</i>	5.20*	5.34*	5.42*	5.6*
K ₂ SO ₄	{ Conc.	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20
	{ <i>p_H</i>	6.8**	7.1**	7.3**	7.4**
KNO ₃	{ Conc.	0.114	0.171	0.228	0.285
	{ <i>p_H</i>	6.0**	6.2**	6.3**	6.4**

* *p_H* taken by Hellige Immersion colorimeter.

** *p_H* taken by Hellige Disc comparator.

TABLE II.

Arsenious sulphide sol (original).

KCl	{ Conc.	0.215	0.322	0.537	0.752
	{ pH*	3.46	3.48	3.52	4.54
KBr	{ Conc.	0.134	6.201	0.335	0.469
	{ pH*	3.45	2.46	3.58	3.60

TABLE III.

Arsenious sulphide sol (doubly diluted, i.e., 1:1).

KCl	{ Conc.	0.285	0.322	0.537	6.752
	{ pH*	3.66	3.66	3.67	3.70
KBr	{ Conc.	0.134	0.261	0.305	0.460
	{ pH*	3.67	3.67	3.68	3.70

* H₂-electrode was employed. The liquid obtained after coagulation contained a trace of free arsenious oxide and no hydrogen sulphide could be detected with lead acetate. The H₂-electrode gave a consistent and steady *e.m.f.*

TABLE IV.

Change of p_H (by quinhydrone electrode) and Cl' (by Ag-AgCl electrode) ions with different concentrations of electrolytes.

Al (OH)₃ sol. 0.1 N electrolytic concentration of mother electrolyte was used.

Composition.	K ₂ SO ₄ *		K ₂ C ₂ O ₄ **		KNO ₃ †		K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ ¹		NaNO ₃ †		Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄ **		KCl
	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^3$.	
25 c.c. sol + 25 c.c. H ₂ O	4.05	3.32	4.05	3.32	4.05	3.32	4.05	3.32	4.05	3.32	4.05	3.32	4.05
25 c.c. sol + 24 c.c. H ₂ O + 1 c.c. electrolyte	4.09	4.07	4.10	5.49	4.05	3.38	4.187	...	4.12	3.38	4.28	3.63	4.05
25 c.c. sol + 23 c.c. H ₂ O + 2 c.c. electrolyte	4.22	4.07	4.65	5.75	4.09	3.38	4.53	...	4.15	3.31	4.82	4.36	4.09
25 c.c. sol + 22 c.c. H ₂ O + 3 c.c. electrolyte	4.33	4.46	5.63	5.75	4.09	3.38	5.3	...	4.15	3.31	6.17	4.89	4.22
25 c.c. sol + 21 c.c. H ₂ O + 4 c.c. electrolyte	4.28	4.36	6.22	7.24	4.05	3.23	5.4	...	4.12	3.09	6.57	4.89	4.15

* Coagulation took place at all the given concentrations.

** No coagulation took place at all concentrations of the electrolytes excepting at the lowest one.

† No coagulation.

TABLE V.

Change of p_H (by Folien colorimeter) and Cl' ion with Ag-AgCl electrodes with different concentrations of electrolytes.

Fe (OH)₃ Sol (B). 0.1N electrolytic concentration of mother electrolyte was used.

Composition.	K ₂ SO ₄ *		K ₂ C ₂ O ₄ *		KNO ₃ †		NaNO ₃ †		Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄ *	
	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^5$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^5$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^5$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^5$.	p_H .	$Cl' \times 10^5$.
25 c.c. sol + 25 c.c. H ₂ O	6.0	7.46	6.0	7.46	6.0	7.46	6.0	7.46	6.0	7.46
25 c.c. sol + 24 c.c. H ₂ O + 1 c.c. electrolyte	6.2	9.61	6.2-6.4	9.61	6.0	7.46	5.8-6.0	7.19	6.2	10.5
25 c.c. sol + 23 c.c. H ₂ O + 2 c.c. electrolyte	6.2	9.61	6.4-6.6	9.86	6.0	7.46	6.0-6.2	6.98	6.6-6.8	10.5
25 c.c. sol + 22 c.c. H ₂ O + 3 c.c. electrolyte	6.2	9.61	6.4-6.6	9.61	6.0	7.46	6.0-6.2	6.65	7.0-7.2	10.5
25 c.c. sol + 21 c.c. H ₂ O + 4 c.c. electrolyte	6.2	10.5	6.8-7.0	9.61	6.0	7.46	6.0	6.19	7.0-7.2	10.5

* Coagulation took place at all the given concentrations.

† No coagulation.

DISCUSSION.

Variation of p_H .

Ferric hydroxide sol (A) and arsenious sulphide sol (Tables I, III).—The p_H regularly increases with the amount of solid salt added. With arsenious sulphide the increase is much smaller. The concentration of the colloidal solution has also an influence on the p_H . Thomas and Whitehead (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 27) working with aluminium oxide sols observed a regular increase in the p_H below the coagulation concentration which apparently continues after the whole of the colloid is coagulated. Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 35, 1) has observed that though the whole of the sulphate is taken up by the colloid (ferric oxide) so that none of it is left in the intermicellar liquid less than half the equivalent amount of chlorine is displaced from the colloidal particle. With increase in the concentration of the sulphate, the amount of chloride displaced increases linearly but suddenly rises near about the precipitation concentration whereafter it has the form of a typical adsorption isotherm. Weiser (*ibid.*, 1931, 35, 1388) working with aluminium hydroxide sols has recently measured the p_H systematically at concentrations on both sides of the precipitation value. He obtained in most cases a rise in p_H but with potassium sulphate and a particular sol of aluminium oxide, he observed a lowering of the p_H . There is a difference between the experimental conditions used by the above authors and those used by us in that the solid salt has been used.

The order of the coagulation power of the anions for ferric oxide sols is as follows: sulphate > chloride > nitrate > bromide (*vide* Freundlich, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, 44, 151). No such relationship exists between the p_H at equivalent concentrations of the anions and their coagulating powers. The same conclusion has been arrived at by Weiser (*loc. cit.*).

(b) *Ferric hydroxide sol (B) and aluminium hydroxide sol.*—Potassium and sodium nitrates have the least effect on the p_H value of both sols. These electrolytes cause no change of p_H with ferric hydroxide sol while with aluminium hydroxide sol there is a slight change in the p_H values; with the latter sol sodium nitrate increases the p_H slightly but perceptibly. A greater effect of Na⁺ as compared with K⁺ is also noticeable if we compare the two electrolytes Na₂C₂O₄ and K₂C₂O₄. Moreover, comparing KCl with KNO₃

the p_H is relatively greater for the chloride than for the nitrate. C_2O_4'' and SO_4'' have much greater effect on the p_H than Cl' or NO_3' . The difference may be partially explained if we assume the formation of $H_2C_2O_4$ and H_2SO_4 . There is another possibility. The surface of the colloidal particles of ferric or aluminium oxide may contain simple or complex ion or aluminium ions of different valencies, *e. g.*, Fe^{+++} , $(FeOH)^{++}$ or $(FeOCl)^{++}$ or $(FeO)^+$. SO_4'' or C_2O_4'' ions being divalent the number of Fe^{++} or other higher valent ions disappear more quickly. Assuming an equilibrium between the ions on the surface with hydrogen ions in the solution it would be evident that the stability of higher valent ions which corresponds to higher stages of the dissociation of the base requires a p_H value lower than that for the lower valent ions. The disappearance of the higher valent ions would thus result in a diminution of the hydrogen ion concentration. The stability of these complexes would also depend on the chemical affinity *i. e.* the nature of the ions. Lastly the process of coagulation may affect the p_H by the entrainment of ions or by liberation of a part of the surface ions. SO_4'' has a greater coagulating action than C_2O_4'' on $Al(OH)_3$ sol, but a much smaller effect on the p_H and on the concentration of chlorine than C_2O_4'' .

From Tables IV and V we find the following order of anions regarding their power to increase the p_H values:

For ferric hydroxide sol the order is $C_2O_4'' > SO_4'' > NO_3'$.

For aluminium hydroxide sol the order is $C_2O_4'' > SO_4'' > Cl' > NO_3'$

Variation of Cl' Ion Concentrations.

Ferric hydroxide sol (A) and aluminium hydroxide sol (vide Tables IV and V).—With $Al(OH)_3$ sol KNO_3 has practically no effect on Cl' ion concentrations. $NaNO_3$ shows a slight decrease and then a marked fall at higher concentrations of the electrolytes. With K_2SO_4 and $Na_2C_2O_4$ there is a considerable increase in Cl' ion concentrations. C_2O_4'' has somewhat greater effect as compared to SO_4'' . It appears that with SO_4'' , Cl' is liberated as if on by stages while with C_2O_4'' , Cl' is liberated continually. This difference may be apparent and not real. It is remarkable that in both cases the effect of electrolytes on the variation of p_H and Cl' is somewhat parallel. This may mean breakdown of the original complexes with consequent liberation of Cl' ions and an increase in the p_H on the formation of stabler complexes of lower valency. With aluminium hydroxide sol

$K_2C_2O_4$ has a greater effect, in increasing the Cl' ion concentrations than $Na_2C_2O_4$; with ferric hydroxide sol the opposite behaviour is observed.

Curiously enough, KNO_3 does not increase the Cl' ion concentrations. $NaNO_3$ increases the Cl' ion concentrations of $Al(OH)_3$ sol when the concentration of electrolyte is very low but a fall of the Cl' ion increase is noticed at higher concentrations. In the case of $Fe(OH)_3$ sol there is a continuous fall in Cl' ion concentrations at all concentrations of added electrolyte. The difference in the effects of KNO_3 and $NaNO_3$ on the pH and in the liberation of the chlorine has some points of similarity. C_2O_4'' and SO_4'' increase the Cl' ion concentrations of $Fe(OH)_3$ sol.

The order in which the above anions increases the chlorine ion concentration is as follows:

It will be seen that there is no exact parallelism between coagulation capacity, the liberation of chlorine ions and pH . The reaction that takes place is thus complicated and theoretically one can conceive the following reactions being responsible for the ultimate result: (a) the reaction of the primarily or electrically adsorbed ion and those in the mobile layer with those in solution; (b) the transformation of SO_4'' or C_2O_4'' ions to HSO_4' or HC_2O_4' in the intercellary liquid itself, and (c) the entrainment or liberation of ions and consequent hydrolytic and other changes resulting from agglomeration itself.

SUMMARY.

1. The pH of the supernatant liquid after coagulation of ferric hydroxide (A) and arsenious sulphide sols depends on the nature of the coagulating electrolyte and to a less extent on its amount. With both sols the pH increases on addition of larger amounts of solid electrolytes. With arsenious sulphide sol, the increase in pH is very slight.

2. With ferric hydroxide sol (B) and aluminium hydroxide sol, there is a tendency for increase in pH and Cl' ion concentrations on addition of increasing concentrations of electrolytes.

(a) Potassium and sodium nitrates have the least effect on the p_H value of both sols.

(b) The following orders of anions for increasing the p_H have been observed :

(c) The order in which the anions increase the Cl' ion concentrations are as follows :

(d) Potassium nitrate has got no effect in increasing the Cl' ion concentration of sols.

(e) There is no exact parallelism between coagulating capacity, the liberation of Cl' ions and the p_H .

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